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Targeting the Prion-Like Aggregation of Mutant p53 to Combat Cancer

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Abstract

The team first screened a set of protein mimics originally designed to target Alzheimer's disease and type 2 diabetes. The results identify a mimicry of the protein that potentially isolates the mutated p53 material and prevents further protein accumulation. The researchers then showed that segregation of mutated p53 grains by protein mimicking restored the suppressive function of the p53 tumor, leading to the death of a wide range of cancer cells. Importantly, protein mimicry therapy effectively reduces tumors that contain mutated p53 while showing no significant toxins for healthy tissue, resulting in significantly longer survival. "As the prevalence of cancer increases worldwide, there is an urgent need for new cancer therapies to complement or replace existing therapies," said the study's lead author. Here we show the first successful use of a small molecule amyloid inhibitor as an anticancer agent. We believe that this will have a far-reaching impact, as it effectively bridges the gap between amyloid disease and cancer and is the basis for passing on information approaches in the design of new and robust cancer mutation therapies for the p53 mutation.

Keywords: Cancer; Cells; Tissues, Tumors; Prevention, Prognosis; Diagnosis; Imaging; Screening; Treatment; Management

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Introduction

CAR-T cell therapy is a type of immunotherapy that involves inhibiting the strength of a person's immune system by engineering their T cells to identify and kill cancer cells. The Food

and Drug Administration approved the first CAR-T cell treatment for myeloma in March. Today we are working to treat another potential CAR-T cell for multiple myeloma. The CARTITUDE-1 study is a stage 1B / II clinical trial. The trial targeted B-cell maturation antigen by targeting CAR-T cell therapy in

patients with multiple myeloma who had received at least three previous lines of treatment with standard drugs, including proteasome inhibitors, immunosuppressive drugs, and CD38 antibodies. Tested. Cilta-cel is made from the patient's own T cells, which is genetically engineered and is given as a single injection. The overall response rate to treatment was 97%, while the complete response rate and progression-free survival rate were 67% and 77%, respectively. The overall survival rate was 89%. Updates to this study were recently presented at the annual meeting of the American Clinical Oncology Association after our paper was accepted for publication in The Lancet. Our ASCO presentation showed a deeper response for patients receiving this treatment. These results are very impressive for patients with myeloma who have already undergone many treatment lines for their disease. It will be important to better understand the clinical features of patients who have experienced long-term recovery from this treatment and the mechanisms by which patients' relapse. While it is not possible to formally conduct two separate single-arm studies on the idea of cells and cilia, the rate of dramatic response and progression-free survival of eyelash-treated patients is very interesting. The potential translation of this research into an individual clinical treatment requires the resolution of many logistical details, including ensuring the reliability of the transfer from production for research to a commercial product [1-510].

Results and Discussion

Ketogenic metabolic therapy (KMT) based on ketogenic diets is considered as a potential option or adjunctive therapy for disease control, brain tumor progression. This type of treatment is a non-toxic, complementary or alternative diet that uses low-carb, high-fat diets to treat a variety of malignancies, including glioblastoma. This has been important for people suffering from epilepsy. In addition to the long-term therapeutic effect of the

ketogenic diet, the vital role of metabolism in the health and disease of the central nervous system and throughout the body is well known. New studies have shown that using personal metabolism to fight some tumors may be helpful. After adopting a ketogenic diet, a patient showed that he had refused treatment for his brain tumor and had developed a fatal glioblastoma tumor. Glioblastoma (GBM) is a rapidly growing brain tumor also known as grade 4 astrocytoma, which penetrates the tissues around the brain and kills approximately 15,000 people annually and is incurable. According to the researchers, the survival time after GBM has not yet increased significantly, despite changes in treatment standards and the development of new safe therapies. GBM, like malignant tumors, depends on the simultaneous restriction of fermentable fuels such as glucose and glutamine for energy synthesis and survival.

Conclusions

The cell cycle of such a subject has been thoroughly studied, yet here we are examining for the second time that we have entered a new phase; Biology always has new insights to show us. This data was amazing. This map is based on this beautiful circular pattern that we have identified as all the different stages of the cell cycle. Have a disease. When Placer and colleagues used the ccAF tool to analyze cell data for glioma tumors, we found that tumor cells were often in the G0 or G1 nerve growth state. With tumor aggression, fewer cells remain at rest in the G0 nerve state. This means that more cells are growing and growing in the tumor.

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